

The Church of Christ, Scientist

also known as “Christian Science”

Secondary source

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** Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA*

Entry tags: Religious Group, Christian Science, Christian Traditions, New Religious Movement

The Church of Christ, Scientist, also known as Christian Science, is an American Christian restorationist religion and healing tradition founded by Mary Baker Eddy in 1879. Christian Science is predicated on what's considered Eddy's re-discovery of the divine healing ministry of Jesus Christ as an essential aspect of Christian life. After a lifetime of physical and mental suffering, Eddy founded Christian Science following a debilitating fall on the ice in Lynn, Massachusetts in 1866 referred to as the “Fall in Lynn”. During her period of recovery, she turned to the Bible for relief and later wrote her understanding of Jesus' ministry in a text published in 1875 entitled *Science and Health* (later re-published as *Science and Health with Key to the Scriptures*). Eddy underscored the need for Christians to take part in healing both themselves and others and declared that the same works of healing demonstrated by Jesus were not miracles particular to his age but available to all Christians. Before writing *Science and Health*, Eddy was a student of New Thought leader Phineas Parkhurst Quimby. During the turn of the 20th century, Christian Science rapidly attracted followers across the United States and later in Europe and Australia. Eventually the religion would spread to Asia and Africa, where it now has experienced its greatest growth. The religious practice of Christian Science is based on study of the King James version of the Bible and a large corpus of writings authored by Mary Baker Eddy, especially her work *Science and Health* which is considered the textbook of Christian Science. In lieu of clergy, Christian Scientists instead view the Bible and *Science and Health* as their only “Pastor.” They are most well-known for engaging in healing by prayer rather than seeking allopathic medical care, although they are not forbidden as members of the Church from seeking medical attention. Christian Scientists employ prayer for healing and also hire professional healers in Christian Science known as practitioners. Christian Scientists are called to engage in the healing work of Jesus Christ by healing themselves and others through prayer alone. This prayer involves an understanding of God as Perfect Spirit and man as God's perfect creation. Reality is interpreted as strictly metaphysical or Divine Spirit, and consequently, disease and matter are dismissed as unreal and lacking in “intelligence” and power. Christian Scientists interpret disease as the product of fear or erroneous thinking referred to as “mortal mind” and dismiss epidemiological interpretations of illness and contagion. In the United States, members of the Church of Christ, Scientist have historically labored through lobbying and other means of political redress to maintain what they consider their religious freedom to opt for care under a Christian Science practitioner or healer rather than seeking medical attention. Christian Science has therefore been influential in shaping the United States' legal interpretation of religious freedom. Christian Scientists have been implicated in charges of child neglect and abuse in legal cases in which Christian Science parents opted to heal their children through prayer rather than seeking medical attention. Highly-publicized cases of this nature in the late 20th century brought significant negative attention to Christian Science. The Christian Science church is headquartered in Boston, Massachusetts and is known as the Mother Church. It is also the home of the Christian Science Publishing Society where the *Christian Science Monitor*, an internationally-recognized periodical, is published. The Church also publishes the *Christian Science Journal* and the *Christian Science Sentinel*. Both publications contain public testimonies of Christian Science healing. Christian Science churches hold two services each week, one on Sunday and another on Wednesday. Each is led by two readers, or appointed members of branch churches who read from both the King James Bible and *Science and Health with Key to the Scriptures*. The Wednesday service includes public testimony of healings. In

addition to Christian Science branch churches, Christian Science Reading Rooms are operated in conjunction with each church as a “public face” to the religion and offer a place where members and non-members can access and purchase Christian Science literature. Reading Rooms are operated by Christian Science branch church volunteers. Christian Science is considered a “science” or “divine science” in that the religion’s efficacy regarding healing is understood as demonstrable and repeatable. Christian Scientists additionally understand their faith as adhering to divine laws that supersede natural laws. When Eddy adopted the term science in the late 19th century, the term was in wider circulation and had broader connotations than today.

Date Range: 1866 CE - 2020 CE

Region: Origins of Christian Science

Region tags: Global

This map corresponds to three important locations for the origins of the Church of Christ (Scientist) movement: Lynn and Boston, Massachusetts, both of which are important locations in the life of Mary Baker Eddy. The map also features Oconto, Wisconsin, where the first Church of Christ (Scientist) purpose-built church was erected. The movement would spread to Australia, Canada, Germany, Great Britain, Hong Kong, and South Africa. While the movement was also widespread in the United States at the peak, only the important origins locations in the United States are included on this map.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Gillian Gill, *Mary Baker Eddy*, 1998.
- Source 2: Stephen Gottschalk, *The Emergence of Christian Science in American Religious Life*, 1973
- Source 3: Robert Peel's *Mary Baker Eddy: The Years of Discovery*, *Mary Baker Eddy: The Years of Trial and Mary Baker Eddy: The Years of Authority*

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.marybakereddylibrary.org/research/>
- Source 1 Description: The Mary Baker Eddy Library Research Services / Ask a Research Question
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.longyear.org/>
- Source 2 Description: Longyear Museum -- Includes documentaries and archive of research articles
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.marybakereddylibrary.org/mary-baker-eddy/timeline/>
- Source 3 Description: Mary Baker Eddy Chronology

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://mbepapers.org/>

– Source 1 Description: The Mary Baker Eddy Papers, a project of The Mary Baker Eddy Library "to annotate and digitally publish Mary Baker Eddy's correspondence, sermons, and other manuscript materials."

– Source 2 URL: <https://christiansciencemedia.org/files/2010/03/Science-and-Health-with-Key-to-the-Scriptures.pdf>

– Source 2 Description: PDF of Science and Health with Key to the Scriptures, the textbook of Christian Science

– Source 3 URL: <https://mbeinstitute.org/CManual/ChurchManual.pdf>

– Source 3 Description: Manual of the Mother Church

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Notes: One can become a member of the Church of Christ, Scientist provided the following is true of the applicant: "One who is not a member of any church, excepting a branch church of Christ, Scientist, who loves Christian Science, and reads understandingly the Bible, and Science and Health with Key to the Scriptures, by Reverend Mary Baker Eddy, and other works by this author, and who is Christianly qualified and can enter into full fellowship with the Tenets and Rules of The First Church of Christ, Scientist, in Boston, Massachusetts, is eligible to membership."

Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

Notes: Christian Scientists do not need to be members of a Church to be considered Christian Scientists, but they can apply for Church membership through the Mother Church, or headquarter Church of Christian Science, provided they can confirm the following assessment of themselves "One who is not a member of any church, excepting a branch church of Christ, Scientist, who loves Christian Science, and reads understandingly the Bible, and Science and Health with Key to the Scriptures, by Reverend Mary Baker Eddy, and other works by this author, and who is Christianly qualified and can enter into full fellowship with the Tenets and Rules of The First Church of Christ, Scientist, in Boston, Massachusetts...". Members must also adhere to the tenets of of Christian Science as outlined by Mary Baker Eddy, which are as follows: 1. As adherents of Truth, we take the inspired Word of the Bible as our sufficient guide to eternal Life. 2. We acknowledge and adore one supreme and infinite God. We acknowledge His Son, one Christ; the Holy Ghost or divine Comforter; and man in God's image and likeness. 3. We acknowledge God's forgiveness of sin in the destruction of sin and the spiritual understanding that casts out evil as unreal. But the belief in sin is punished so long as the belief lasts. 4. We acknowledge Jesus' atonement as the evidence of divine, efficacious Love,

unfolding man's unity with God through Christ Jesus the Way-shower; and we acknowledge that man is saved through Christ, through Truth, Life, and Love as demonstrated by the Galilean Prophet in healing the sick and overcoming sin and death. 5. We acknowledge that the crucifixion of Jesus and his resurrection served to uplift faith to understand eternal Life, even the allness of Soul, Spirit, and the nothingness of matter. 6. And we solemnly promise to watch, and pray for that Mind to be in us which was also in Christ Jesus; to do unto others as we would have them do unto us; and to be merciful, just, and pure.

↳ Assigned by personal choice:
– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:
– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:
– No

↳ Assigned by gender:
– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:
– No

↳ Assigned by some other factor:
– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: However, the Christian Science Church operates the Christian Science Publishing Society, which publishes the Christian Science Monitor, an internationally-known newspaper, the Christian Science Journal and the Christian Science Sentinel, all of which are publicly available and could conceivably attract followers to Christian Science. Christian Science churches are operate Reading Rooms, which offer more of a public face to the religion and provide a space where outsiders can purchase Christian Science literature and ask questions.

Does the religion have official political support

– I don't know

Notes: In the mid-20th century, several politicians were members of Christian Science and therefore found favor to some degree.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– No

Notes: However, they can be excommunicated.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Estimated range from 100,000-400,000 worldwide. The Church does not publish membership statistics so an exact number is not possible.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 100

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The primary Scripture is the King James version of the Bible. Science and Health is considered the textbook of Christian Science and both are seen as the only “pastor” of the church.

Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: The Bible and Science and Health with Key to the Scriptures by Mary Baker Eddy

Are they oral:

– No

Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– No

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: Christian Scientist view the Bible as being revealed by God who does not exactly fit the database's description of either a supernatural or high god in that He is understood to be the Supreme Lord, the All-in-all without any comparable power and from which all power is sourced.

↳ Inspired by high god:

– No

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: Christian Scientists believe that Science and Health was revealed to Mary Baker Eddy beginning in 1866. After falling on the ice in Lynn, Massachusetts, Eddy became bed-bound and turned to the Bible for relief. She later published her understanding of the Bible and especially Jesus' healing ministry as Science and Health in 1875.

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: There is no clergy in Christian Science. The Bible and Science and Health can be interpreted by all who read them without human intercessory.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: However, each Christian Science church has two appointed "readers" who read selections from the Bible and Science and Health during Church services on Sundays and Wednesdays.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: The Bible and Science and Health are not only the canon of scriptures but are believed to be the literal "Pastor" of the Church. According to Eddy, this decision to bar human pastors in favor of the Bible and Science and Health would ensure that the scriptures were transmitted without the interference of human interpretations and constitute a "sermon undivorced from truth, uncontaminated and unfettered by human hypotheses, and divinely authorized," as she put it.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: This refers to the Church's headquarters church known as the Mother Church in Boston, Massachusetts.

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– I don't know

Notes: The Mother Church in Boston is the largest Christian Science Church in the World. It was constructed in 1894 and was greatly expanded in 1906.

– I don't know

Notes: A granite pyramid was erected to mark the birthplace of Mary Baker Eddy in Bow, New Hampshire. It was dedicated in 1921 marking the centennial of her birth. In 1962, the pyramid was destroyed by order of the Church's Board of Directors in order to prevent the monument from becoming a pilgrimage site.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious

monuments:

– I don't know

Notes: The Christian Science Plaza in Boston, Massachusetts occupies 13.5 acres. This property includes the Mother Church, the Christian Science Publishing House where the Christian Science Monitor is published and the Mary Baker Eddy Library is located, the Sunday School Building, the Church Colonnade Building, an Administration Building and a large reflecting pool.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Notes: It is very limited when present, if present at all. Christian Science churches are known for being very sparsely decorated and devoid of images.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– No

Notes: Not exactly, but the Mother Church in Boston nonetheless represents spiritual and historical import among members of Christian Science.

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: Pilgrimages were actively avoided against with the destruction of the monument erected at Eddy's birthplace in Bow, New Hampshire in 1962.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: Spirit is believed to be the only reality in Christian Science. According to Science and Health's Scientific Statement of Being, "There is no life, truth, intelligence, nor substance in matter. All is infinite Mind and its infinite manifestation, for God is All-in-all." In this view, the foundation of all creation and reality is Spirit. Spirit is one of the seven synonyms Eddy used to refer to God, the others being Mind, Soul, Principle, Life, Truth, and Love. Sin and disease have no reality in Christian Science since God is understood as All-in-all, perfect and harmonious. Humans, as reflections of God, therefore cannot be diseased or sinful. States of disease or illness are therefore interpreted as a form of illusion or "mortal

mind" that conflates matter with being the source of its own power, when instead Spirit is the only source of life.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: Only Spirit has "intelligence" or power, whereas the body as matter is viewed as lacking all intelligence or power and derives its power solely from Spirit.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: There is no death in Christian Science, instead the "afterlife" is viewed as a continuation of this life. Death cannot occur because humans have no life apart from God and since God is eternal humans are also understood as eternal.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

Notes: Christian Scientists interpret death as just another stage in man's immortal and eternal life.

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Notes: Christian Science does not prescribe any form of burial nor funerary practices.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– No

Notes: Eddy was vehemently against any practice akin to Spiritualism, or one that believed in the existence of spirits or ghosts. An entire chapter of Science and Health is dedicated to this topic because during its early period Christian Science was conflated with Spiritualism.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus Christ is believed to be the Messiah who through his life, death and resurrection demonstrated the supremacy and eternity of Spirit over matter. Jesus is considered to be the Savior of all, saving humankind from disease, sickness and death. However, Jesus the historical man is understood to be distinct from the Christ Spirit. Jesus is nonetheless considered the greatest human representation of the Christ. The Christ is believed to be omnipresent and eternal, thus existing before the historical Jesus and expressed before him, in the Hebrew prophets for instance.

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

↳ Alive, identified:

– No

↳ Coming in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: It is believed that the Messiah in the form of Jesus Christ has already come and the Kingdom of Heaven has already been established on Earth.

↳ Coming on specified date:

– No

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future:

– No

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:

– No

↳ Coming has already passed:

– Yes

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs:

– No

Notes: Jesus the Christ is understood to be the greatest human representation of the Christ Spirit. The Christ and Jesus are distinct though in that Jesus was a historical man and the Christ Spirit is eternal and had manifested before Jesus through the persons of the Hebrew prophets and remains ever-present today.

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

Notes: To save mankind from sin, disease and death.

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: This is true except when it comes to seeking medical attention. Instead, Christian Scientists are taught to rely on healing by prayer alone. This form of healing is not mind cure or dependent on one's human will but is rather dependent on the Christ power, as it is referred to.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present and clear

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– Yes

Notes: This relates to the Christian Science understanding of health. For instance, disease and illness are interpreted products of "mortal mind" in that one, being fundamentally Spirit and eternal, cannot be diseased or ill.

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– I don't know

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals (any time period)

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Christian Scientists are called to live Christlike lives by practicing forgiveness, love and compassion.

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

Notes: Christian Scientists follow the Ten Commandments and the teachings of Christ Jesus.

- ↳ Courage (in battle):
 - I don't know
- ↳ Courage (generic):
 - I don't know
- ↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:
 - Yes
- ↳ Generosity / charity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
 - Yes
- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
 - No
- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
 - Yes
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Yes

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– I don't know

↳ Strength (physical):

– No

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– No

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– I don't know

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes [specify]: healing through prayer of oneself and others

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: While Church membership is not dependent on such a constraint, many Christian Scientists practice abstinence before marriage.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: While the Church does not "require" prayer, time spent in prayer and time spent studying the Bible as well as Science and Health is expected of Christian Scientists. Regular Church participation is also generally expected.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Notes: However, some may interpret a Christian Scientists' choice to rely on healing by prayer a form of physical risk-taking, especially in instances where physical relief through allopathic medicine could be readily obtained. In cases involving ill children, this decision has historically been especially controversial and has resulted in a number of court cases in the United States regarding issues of religious freedom, child neglect and parental autonomy. In the 1990s, Christian Scientist parents were convicted of a number of charges including involuntary manslaughter, felony child abuse and child endangerment for choosing healing through prayer by a Christian Science practitioner for their ill children rather than seeking medical attention for them. Christian Scientists have pointed to the number of deaths that have occurred under allopathic medical care as a means of defending their position to opt for prayer.

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: However, while opting for healing by prayer is often considered an ethical precept belonging to Christian Science, Scientists are not prohibited from seeking allopathic medical care. Many Scientists both seek medical means of healing and rely on prayer. At the same time, if one is a member of a branch church, one's roles in the Church can be limited if one is routinely seeking allopathic care over prayer. Reliance on prayer for healing can either be self-guided, that is, one can pray for healing for oneself or it can involve hiring a Christian Science practitioner to heal them through prayer. This kind of healing does not necessitate that the patient and the practitioner or healer be in the same place. Remote healings are in fact very common.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: No clear distinction.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Notes: Christian Scientists operate a number of benevolent associations or Christian Science nursing facilities for those who require extended care. Christian Scientists do not employ drugs in treatments but instead rely on prayer alone.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: Christian Scientists can enroll in what's called Primary Class instruction taught by a trained

Christian Science teacher. This class was designed by Mary Baker Eddy and is based on the chapter entitled Recapitulation in Science and Health. Some Christian Scientists attend Principia College, a private liberal arts school located in Elsah, Illinois. While the College is not run by the Church of Christ, Scientist, it is dedicated to "serving the cause of Christian Science."

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Christian Scientists attend a variety of secular institutions for education.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: Christian Science maintains a highly elaborate bureaucracy governed by the Mother Church in Boston. At the same time, other than abiding by the Mother Church's bylaws as outlined in the Manual of the Mother Church, each branch Church maintains independence and self-determination.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Excepting municipal and state governments.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

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General References

Reference: The Church of Christ, Scientist, Gottschalk, Stephen. *The Emergence of Christian Science in American Religious Life*. University of California Press, 1973.

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